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Determination of pesticide residues in high oil vegetal commodities by using various multi-residue methods and clean-ups followed by liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry

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ABSTRACT

Several extraction methods were evaluated in terms of recoveries and extraction precision for 113 pesticides in avocado: QuEChERS with various d-SPE clean-ups (Z-Sep, Z-Sep+, PSA + C18 and silica), miniLuke and ethyl acetate. Extracts were analysed using liquid chromatography coupled with triple quadrupole mass spectrometer working in multi-reaction monitoring mode. Z-Sep and Z-Sep+ are new types of material for high lipid matrices – these two sorbents contain ZrO_2 , which improves fat removal from the extracts. The QuEChERS protocol with Z-Sep provided the highest number of pesticides with recoveries in the 70–120% range along with the lowest amount of coextracted matrix compounds. Subsequently, this method was validated in two matrices – avocado and almonds. In the validation recoveries at two levels – 10 and 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ – limit of quantitation, linearity, matrix effects, as well as the inter- and intraday precision were studied. In the avocado samples, 107 analytes had LOQs equal to 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ (signal to noise of quantitative transition was equal 20 or more). In the almond samples, 92 pesticides had LOQs equal to 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ ($S/N \geq 20$) and 2 pesticides at 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. The validated method was employed in the analysis of real avocado and almond samples.

Keywords: LC-MS/MS; High oil matrices; Multiresidue methods; Pesticides analysis

1. Introduction

Pesticide analysis of commodities containing high amounts of lipids produces more difficulties than low or non-fatty matrices. The main problem is in obtaining an extract which contains the target analytes but no fat [1,2].

Representative commodities with high oil content are avocado and almonds. Avocado contains up to 30% fat. The major components of avocado fat are fatty acids (oleic, palmitic and linoleic) and triglycerides [3]. The oil content in almonds is higher, at around 50%. The major fatty acids present in almonds are the same as those in avocado [4].

Before injecting into the LC system, it is imperative to remove as much as possible of the fat because any fat presence in the sample may influence chromatographic separation [5]. The amount of fat in the final extract depends on the extraction solvent as well as on the clean-up procedure applied. Lipids are readily soluble in solvents such as ethyl acetate, n-hexane or diethyl ether [6]. To limit fat transfer into the extract, a better choice is acetonitrile – nevertheless, a certain amount of lipids may still find their way into the extract. Moreover, acetonitrile may be an inefficient extraction solvent for lipophilic pesticides because these compounds remain in undissolved fat [7]. Likewise, methanol, as a polar solvent, is not good for lipophilic substances [6] – which may be the reason for the low recoveries of some pesticides [2].

The most common methods for fat removal from extract are low temperature precipitation (freezing-out), gel permeation chromatography (GPC) and adsorption (dispersive solid-phase extraction, solid-phase extraction). Freezing-out is the simplest method for fat removal from the extract. Fat is precipitated in the freezer and subsequently separated by centrifugation. Unfortunately, this method is time consuming and does not remove all the fat so usually some further clean-up is necessary [8,9]. Gel permeation chromatography helps to separate low molecular mass compounds, such as pesticides, from high molecular mass compounds, such as lipids [10]. However, some pesticides have high molecular mass (e.g. pyrethroids) and cannot be separated from lipids with GPC [11]. Some authors have found GPC to be the best clean-up method for high oil samples [11], whereas others obtained better results with d-SPE [9]. In column SPE and d-SPE clean-up, similar sorbents can be applied: C18 [7-9,12], PSA [7,8,12,13], Florisil [8], Oasis HLB [14,15] and GCB [8,13].

Over the last decade, various extraction methods of LC amenable pesticides from

fatty matrices were proposed. Granby et al. validated methanol-water extraction for 19 pesticides from avocado. This method was simple with only three steps: ultrasonication, centrifugation and filtering [16]. A methanol-water mixture was also applied by Hernandez et al., however number of investigated analytes was higher (52 pesticides), as clean-up Oasis HLB cartridges were used [14]. Other authors proposed clean-up of methanol-water extracts using ChemElut columns [17]. In addition, some variations of the QuEChERS [18] method were examined. Lehotay et al. tested acetate-buffered QuEChERS [7]. Unbuffered QuChERS was proposed as an extraction method for pesticides from olives [1] and avocado [19]. For pesticide extraction from high oil fruit and vegetable matrices, solid-phase dispersion [1,20], miniLuke [21] and pressurised liquid extraction [6] were also tested. To the best of our knowledge, the available literature on pesticide determination methods in almonds is very limited [22].

The main aim of the work was to evaluate Z-Sep and Z-Sep+ sorbents as clean-up materials for pesticide analysis in avocado and almonds. Z-Sep+ is a silica carrier coated with zirconium dioxide and octadecylsilane groups. Z-Sep is, in fact, a mixture of two sorbents – C18 and silica coated with zirconium dioxide, the proportion of $ZrO_2/C18$ is 2/5. Zirconium dioxide is an amphoteric oxide. Distinct classes of active sites exist on its surface – the Lewis acid sites, the Brønsted acid sites and the Brønsted base sites. Adsorption on the Brønsted sites is pH dependent. At low pH, the surface is protonated and behaves like an acid – under these conditions anions are adsorbed. At high pH, the zirconia surface has a negative charge (basic character) and cation adsorption is possible [23]. Zirconium dioxide is a good adsorbent of carboxylic acids. Thistlethwaite et al. investigated oleic acid adsorption of oleic acid. In pH 6 and lower they found very strong adsorption of oleate anions. They concluded that adsorption was strong thanks to electrostatic interaction between oleate anions and the positively-charged zirconium dioxide surface [24]. The presence of a double bond in the carboxylic acid molecule may increase adsorption. Furthermore, dicarboxylic acids adsorb more strongly than mono-carboxylic acids because more stable structures are formed [25]. α -Hydroxycarboxylic acids adsorb via both functional groups – carboxylic and hydroxylic. It was also found that in the adsorption of aromatic carboxylic acids, only functional groups containing oxygen took part, whereas thiol groups did not [26]. Zr(IV) sites are hard Lewis acids so they strongly adsorb hard Lewis bases as $R-SO_3^-$, $R-PO_3^-$ and $R-COO^-$. In this kind of interaction, the desorption kinetic is very slow [27]. Lewis acid-Lewis base interactions do not depend on pH. In the reaction, a

coordinated bond is formed. Zr atoms are electron acceptors (Lewis acids) because they have vacant 3d orbitals. Adsorbed molecules are electron donors (Lewis bases). This theory explains adsorption of oleate anions at pH 9 [24] and adsorption of phospholipids from oil [28]. It was postulated that the presence of Lewis acid sites is responsible for the irreversible adsorption of proteins on the ZrO₂ surface. Numerous carboxylic groups in the protein molecule make adsorption very strong [29].

2. Experimental

2.1. Reagents and materials

All high purity pesticide standards were obtained from Dr. Ehrenstorfer (Augsburg, Germany) and Riedel-de Haën (Selze, Germany) and were stored at -30 °C. Individual pesticide stock solutions (1000–2000 mg/L) were prepared in acetonitrile and ethyl acetate and were stored in amber screw-capped glass vials in the dark at -20 °C. Individual standard solutions, used for the optimisation, and two standard-mix solutions, used for the calibration, were prepared from the stock standards.

Ultra gradient HPLC-grade acetonitrile was obtained from Sigma–Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). Dichloromethane and HPLC- grade ethyl acetate were purchased from Fluka (Steinheim, Germany). Petroleum ether was supplied by Riedel-de Haën (Seelze, Germany). Acetone pa. was purchased from J.T.Baker (Steinheim, Germany). Methanol was obtained from Sigma–Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). Citrate dehydrate and silica were purchased from Fluka (Steinheim, Germany). Sodium chloride was purchased from J.T.Baker (Deventer, Holland). Disodium hydrogencitrate sesquihydrate was obtained from Sigma–Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). Anhydrous magnesium sulphate was supplied by Panreac (Barcelona, Spain). C18 was purchased from Agilent Technologies (Santa Clara, CA). PSA, Z-Sep and Z-Sep+ were obtained from Supelco (Bellefonte, PA). A Milli-Q-Plus ultra-pure water system from Milli-pore (Milford, MA, USA) was used throughout the study to obtain the HPLC-grade water used during the analyses and to hydrate the almonds.

2.2. Spiking procedure

For recovery studies, the sample obtained from the local market was spiked with the standard solution in methanol at the appropriate level. Prior analysis of the sample was performed in order to ensure it did not contain any of the studied compounds, and this sample was selected as a blank for spiking, calibration curves, and recovery purposes. 70 g of minced avocado was weighed and transferred to a beaker and the sample was fortified homogeneously with 700 μL of the appropriate mix and then the mixture was blended for 30 min. In the case of almonds, 40 g were placed in a crystallizer, where they were spiked with 20 mL of the working standard solution in methanol. Following this, the sample was blended thoroughly for 30 min under a nitrogen stream until dryness. The samples were allowed to stand at room temperature prior to analysis. The final spiking concentration levels in the sample used for recovery studies were 10 and 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$.

2.3. Extraction procedures

Methods which are in widespread use were evaluated for fatty matrices testing. The selected methods were QuEChERS (with different clean-ups: PSA-C18, silica, Z-Sep and Z-Sep+), ethyl acetate method [30] and mini-Luke [31]. The only modifications of the methods from [30,31] were the application of surrogate standards (malathion- d_{10} and TPP), an injection standard (dimethoate- d_6) and the reconstitution step was carried out as it is described in Section 2.3.1.

2.3.1. QuEChERS method

The well-known and accepted QuEChERS sample preparation procedure was applied to the samples [32]. After homogenisation, a 10 g portion of avocado, or 5 g in the case of almonds, was weighed in a 50 mL PTFE centrifuge tube. To almonds samples 5 mL of water were added, samples were shaken and left for 30 minutes. After that, 10 mL of acetonitrile and 50 μL of a mix of surrogate standards at 10 mg/L – triphenyl phosphate (TPP) and malathion- d_{10} – were added and the samples were shaken in an automatic axial extractor (AGYTAX[®], Cirta Lab. S.L., Spain) for 4 min. Afterwards, 4 g of magnesium sulphate, 1 g of sodium chloride, 1 g of trisodium citrate dihydrate and 0.5 g of disodium hydrogencitrate sesquihydrate were added and the samples were again shaken in the automatic axial extractor for 4 min. The extract was then centrifuged (3700 rpm) for 5 min. 5 mL of the supernatant were transferred to a 15 mL PTFE centrifuge tube containing

750 mg of magnesium sulphate and (a) 125 mg of PSA and 125 mg of C18, (b) 175 mg of Z-Sep, (c) 175 mg of Z-Sep+, (d) 150 mg of silica. The extract was shaken in a vortex for 30 s and centrifuged again (3700 rpm) for a further 5 min. Subsequently, 250 μ L of the extract were evaporated under a gentle nitrogen stream. To dry vial 150 μ L (avocado samples) or 200 μ L (almonds samples) of acetonitrile were added and the vials were vortexed. Subsequently, the vials were filled up to 500 μ L with water and shaken again. Prior to injection into the LC-MS/MS system, the samples were filtered through a 0.45 μ m PTFE filter (Millex FG, Millipore, Mildford, MA, USA). 10 μ L of dimethoate- d_6 2.5 μ g/L were added to each vial as injection control standard. With this treatment, 1 mL of sample extract represents 0.5 g of avocado sample and 0.25 g of almond.

2.4. Analysis

2.4.1. Liquid chromatography–triple quadrupole-mass spectrometry analysis

For LC analysis, an Agilent 1200 HPLC system with a binary pump was used. It was equipped with a reversed-phase C8 analytical column of 4.6 mm \times 150 mm and 5 μ m particle size (Agilent Zorbax SB). Compounds were separated using acetonitrile (mobile phase A) and milliQ water with 0.1% formic acid (mobile phase B). The flow rate was kept constant at 0.6 mL/min and the gradient programme was set as follows: 20% A (initial conditions) was kept constant for 3 min followed by a linear gradient up to 100% A in 27 min, after which the mobile phase composition was maintained at 100% A for 3 min. The re-equilibration time was 5 min. The injection volume was 10 μ L. For the mass spectrometric analysis, a 6490 QqQ MS/MS system (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA) equipped with an electrospray ionisation source (ESI) operating in positive ionisation mode was applied using DMRM (dynamic multi-reaction monitoring) software features. The ESI source settings were gas temperature, 120 $^{\circ}$ C; gas flow, 15 L/min; nebuliser gas, 35 psi; sheath gas temperature, 375 $^{\circ}$ C; sheath gas flow, 12 L/min; capillary voltage, 3500 V; nozzle voltage, 300 V. The iFunnel parameters were high pressure RF 150 V and low pressure RF 60 V. Nitrogen was served as the nebuliser and collision gas. Mass Hunter Data Acquisition; Qualitative Analysis and Quantitative Analysis software (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, v.B.06 and v.B.05) was used for method development and data acquisition.

2.4.2. Optimisation of LC-MS/MS parameters

In order to obtain the maximum sensitivity for identification and quantification of the target compounds, careful optimisation of all MS parameters was performed. The parameters optimised were: collision energy (CE), gas temperature, gas flow, sheath gas temperature, sheath gas flow, high and low pressure RF. The best sensitivity in multiple reaction monitoring operation mode was achieved through the acquisition of single reaction monitoring (SRM) transitions under DMRM conditions and with a time window of 60 s (the instrument acquires each SRM data only ± 30 s from the retention time). The MS operated in SRM mode with a resolution set to Unit for Q1 and Q3. For the identification of analytes, the EU guidelines for LC-MS/MS analysis were considered (Document N° SANCO/12495/2011) [33]. The values of the parameters optimised and the SRM transitions selected in the analytical method are shown in Table 1. The most intense SRM transition was selected for quantitation purposes (SRM1).

2.5. Validation of the analytical procedure

A validation study was performed in terms of recovery, linearity, limit of quantitation, matrix effects, as well as intra-day and inter-day precision. The recoveries and precision of the extraction method were determined as the average of five replicates of spiked blank matrix analysed at concentration levels of 10 and 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. A further part of the validation procedure for the method was carried out using spiked extracts. The LC-(QqQ)MS system's linearity was evaluated by assessing the signal responses of the target analytes from matrix-matched calibration solutions prepared by spiking blank extracts at seven concentration levels – from 0.5 to 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ in the vial for avocado and 0.25 to 125 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ for almonds – which correspond to 1–500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ in the sample due to the 2 and 4-times dilution factor. The level of quantitation (LOQ) was set as the minimum concentration that can be quantified with acceptable accuracy and precision, as described in Document No. SANCO/12495/2011 [33]. For the assessment of ion suppression/enhancement effects, chromatograms of standard solution and spiked sample extracts at the same concentration levels were compared. The precision of the chromatographic method (represented as the relative standard deviation, RSD %) was obtained from the repeated injection (five times) of a spiked extract at vial concentration levels of 5 and 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ for avocado and 2.5 and 12.5 for almonds. Precision is expressed as RSD (%) of the intra-day and inter-day analyses ($n=5$) over 1 and 5 days, respectively.

2.6. Real samples

In order to check the method, 25 avocado samples and 18 of almond were purchased in different local shops in Almería (south-eastern Spain). Packs weighed from 100 to 1000 g. All samples were stored in their original packaging under the recommended conditions prior to use.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Method selection

During the preliminary experiments the importance of the reconstitution method was noticed. Since the final extracts were in organic solvents, before the injection, samples had to be evaporated and redissolved in solvent which ensure good chromatographic peak shape. At the beginning of the experiments, evaporated samples of avocado were redissolved in a mixture containing 10% (v/v) of acetonitrile in water. This composition was weaker than the initial mobile phase in the chromatographic separation method. As is presented in Fig. 1a, all the types of clean-up applied in QuEChERS gave similar results – due to an incorrect reconstitution conditions. However, when the reconstitution approach described in Section 2.3.1 was applied, recovery values rose. Moreover, differences in clean-up sorbent effectiveness became more pronounced. Even after reconstitution with higher amount of acetonitrile, on the bottom of vials with extract from PSA + C18 clean-up was present a sediment whereas bottoms of vials from Z-Sep clean-up were clear. To investigate role of that sediment both types of extracts were analysed again, but this time, after evaporation, were reconstituted in ethyl acetate and injected into GC-MS/MS. Ethyl acetate assured complete reconstitution of samples. In supplementary data (Table S1) presented are recoveries obtained in both systems. Pesticides are segregated according to decreasing value of pK_{ow} (from lipophilic to hydrophilic). For non-polar pesticides characteristic is that recoveries from extracts cleaned with PSA + C18 and analysed by LC are considerably lower than in the other three cases. However for polar pesticides all four analyses gave similar results.

Probable explanation of this phenomena is that PSA + C18 were not able to adsorb some matrix compounds (see Section 3.2.5). Those compounds were poorly soluble

in water and trapped non-polar pesticides in undissolved layer on the bottom of the vial.

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2013.06.070>.

For almond the influence of the reconstitution method on recoveries was also checked. In the case of almond extracts, it was necessary to increase the amount of acetonitrile to 40% (Fig. 1b).

In case of sensitive instruments evaporation/reconstitution can be replaced by a simple dilution of the extract.

During initial studies different extraction methods were compared. To simplify the procedure, only one spiking level in one matrix (50 µg/kg in avocado) was investigated. Only recovery values and relative standard deviations were considered. Three well known multi-residue methods were selected for comparison: the ethyl acetate method, miniLuke and QuEChERS. However, in the case of the latter method, four types of d-SPE clean-up (PSA + C18, silica, Z-Sep, Z-Sep+) were checked. As is presented in Fig. 1a, the highest number of pesticides with recoveries in the 70–120% range was provided using QuEChERS with Z-Sep sorbent – as well as the best recoveries, Z-Sep also ensured the lowest average RSD values. The second best method was ethyl acetate extraction although this offered lower recovery values than Z-Sep, and the extracts contained large amounts of fat which were easily visible after a few hours at –20 °C. For authors simplicity and quickness of the method were very important hence freezing-out and gel permeation chromatography were not considered. The amounts of fat were so great in the ethyl acetate extracts (Supplementary material, Fig. S1) that the application of a Z-Sep or Z-Sep+ clean-up step did nothing to improve it. Based on all available information, QuEChERS with Z-Sep was selected for further studies. Other authors also found Z-Sep provided better clean-up than Z-Sep+ or PSA + C18 [34]. For almonds, two sorbents were tested: Z-Sep and Z-Sep+. Again, Z-Sep assured better recoveries (94 pesticides with recoveries from 70% to 120%) than Z-Sep+ (75 pesticides).

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3.2. QuEChERS validation

3.2.1. Recoveries

For recovery experiments, two fortification levels were selected: 10 µg/kg and 50 µg/kg. In avocado, at the 50 µg/kg level, 107 of 113 pesticides had recoveries within the 70–120% range (Table 2). The six pesticides with lower recoveries were: cyromazine, ethirimol, nitenpyram, pymetrozine, quinoxyfen and thiophanate-methyl. A similar situation occurred at the 10 µg/kg level. It is difficult to unambiguously point to the reason for the low recoveries of cyromazine, ethirimol, nitenpyram, pymetrozine, quinoxyfen and thiophanate-methyl. These pesticides have different properties, nitenpyram and cyromazine have high water solubility (840,000 mg/L and 13,000 mg/L, respectively) whereas the remaining four are much less water soluble (from 0.1 mg/L to 270 mg/L). Furthermore, the octanol-water partition coefficient differs greatly between the pesticides, the pK_{ow} values vary from -0.069 to 4.66. Poor recoveries for quinoxyfen and thiophanate-methyl extracted from avocado using the QuEChERS method have been reported in the literature [19].

In almonds, at the 50 µg/kg level, 94 pesticides had recoveries within the 70–120% range and at the 10 µg/kg level, there were 92. In this matrix, the relation between the physical properties of the analytes and their recovery values is more pronounced. The majority of pesticides with low recoveries have a pK_{ow} higher than 4; however, there are exceptions. The relationships between pK_{ow} and recoveries are presented in Fig. 2.

It was noticed generally that non-polar pesticides had higher recoveries in avocado than in almonds. At the 50 µg/kg level, out of the 20 pesticides with the highest pK_{ow} values (the most lipophilic), only 3 had similar recoveries in both matrices; the remaining 17 gave far better results in avocado. In the case of the hydrophilic pesticides, this tendency did not appear. This difference is the result of the higher fat content in almonds along with the poor solubility of fat in acetonitrile.

In both matrices, RSD values ($n = 5$) were below 20% for all analytes. Values of recoveries and RSD are presented in Table 2.

3.2.2. Limits of quantitation

According to the DG Sanco guidelines [33], the limit of quantitation is the lowest spiked level which meets the criteria of a mean recovery within the 70–120% range and an $RSD \leq 20\%$. In the results presented, only two LOQ values (10 and 50 µg/kg) were evaluated. In avocado, 107 analytes had limits of quantitation equal to 10 µg/kg; whilst 6 pesticides had recoveries outside the 70–120% range. In almonds, 92

pesticides had LOQs at 10 µg/kg and 2 pesticides had LOQs at 50 µg/kg. The remaining 19 analytes had recoveries that were too low. For all pesticides at level 10 µg/kg, in avocado as well as in almonds, signal to noise of quantitative transition was equal or higher than 20. Thanks to this it is possible to apply the method for concentration levels lower than 10 µg/kg. Values of LOQ are presented in Table 3.

3.2.3. Linearity

For all analytes in both matrices, the detector response was linear with a coefficient of determination (r^2) equal to or higher than 0.99 and residuals lower than 20%. However, the linear range was different – in avocado, in most cases, the linear range started at a concentration of 1 or 2 ppb and the detector response was linear up to 500 µg/kg (Table 3). Signals for pesticides such as fenpyroximate, formetanate, metalaxyl, pencycuron, propamocarb, propyzamide, pyraclostrobin, pyridaben, spinosyn A and tebufenozide were linear up to 200 µg/kg and pymetrozine only up to 50 µg/kg. These pesticides are characterised by high sensitivity and so, above mentioned concentrations, the detector was saturated. In almonds, the majority of pesticides were linear from 1 ppb up to 500 µg/kg, only pymetrozine was linear up to 200 µg/kg. In this matrix, detector saturation was not a problem because samples were diluted four times whereas avocado samples were diluted only twice.

3.2.4. Inter and intraday precision

Supplementary data contain Table S2 where precision values are presented for the chromatographic method expressed as intra-day ($n = 5$) and inter-day (over 5 days) precision. The $RSD \leq 20\%$ criterion, recommended by the DG-Sanco guidelines [33], was met by all compounds in both matrices.

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2013.06.070>.

3.2.5. Matrix effects

In complex matrices, such as fruit and vegetables, the analyte signal may be enhanced or suppressed compared to the signal of the same analyte when injected in solvent. Analytical signal interference caused by coeluting sample components is called matrix effects [1]. In LC/MS with electrospray ionisation, signal suppression is more common. Competition between matrix components and analytes to obtain

available protons is responsible for this phenomena as the amount of protons is limited [5]. Signal enhancement is less frequent in LC/MS-ESI. A possible explanation for this is coelution of isobaric ions [19].

An assessment of matrix effects can be carried out by comparing the slopes of analyte calibration plots in solvent and in the investigated matrix. For this purpose, the following equation can be used:

$$ME (\%) = \frac{\text{slope of calibration curve in matrix}}{\text{slope of calibration curve in solvent}} - 1 \times 100$$

Values of ME are presented in Table 3. Soft matrix effects (suppression or enhancement of 0–20%) are negligible. However, if some of the analytes suffer medium (suppression or enhancement of 20–50%) or strong (suppression or enhancement >50%) matrix effects, it is necessary to use certain methods to overcome the influence of the matrix on the analytes. Problems of signal suppression or enhancement can be solved by employing a matrix-matched calibration standard or sample dilution [5].

In avocado, 58 pesticides had soft matrix effects, 37 had medium and 18 had strong matrix effects. In almonds, 100 pesticides had soft matrix effect, 12 medium and 1 strong. However, it cannot be said that almond has less influence on the analysis because almond samples were diluted four times whereas avocado samples were diluted only twice. As was mentioned before, diluting is one of the ways to reduce matrix effects. Nevertheless, it is worth noticing that in almonds, suppressed pesticides appeared at the beginning of the chromatogram (pymetrozine 3.48 min; oxamyl 7.61 min; cyromazine 3.39 min; carbendazim 4.67 min) whereas in avocado, those that were suppressed had long retention times (spirodiclofen 32.87 min; spiromesifen 32.76 min; chlorpyriphos 30.67 min and pyridaben 32.1 min).

To evaluate the amount of matrix compounds in the final extract, LC QToF (6530 Accurate Mass QTOF-MS, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA) was employed. A QToF spectrometer, working in full-scan mode, has the ability to record an unlimited number of compounds [35]. Four extracts (two avocado and two almond) were evaporated and reconstituted in acetonitrile and water (40% of ACN). Final concentration of the samples was equal to 0.25 g/mL. Samples were injected into LC QToF and analysed in full-scan mode. The objective of the experiment was to compare the effectiveness of two different d-SPE clean-up

compositions. In the first case, acetonitrile extract was cleaned with MgSO_4 , PSA and C18 and in the second with MgSO_4 and Z-Sep. To obtain the number of compounds present in each of the extracts, the data were processed with MassHunter software. In avocado, 56,344 compounds were present in the extract prepared with the typical QuEChERS clean-up (MgSO_4 , PSA, C18) whereas in the extract treated with MgSO_4 and Z-Sep, there were 46,819. In almond, the difference between the two clean-up compositions was smaller but still noticeable 45,607 (MgSO_4 , PSA, C18) and 41,270 (MgSO_4 , Z-Sep). From the presented data, it is clear that Z-Sep removes more matrix compounds than PSA and C18, both from avocado and from almond extracts.

The effectiveness of d-SPE sorbents can also be assessed by visual comparison of full-scan chromatograms. The chromatograms obtained in the experiments described above are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. The almond extract chromatograms are practically identical. However, in the case of avocado extracts, the advantage of Z-Sep sorbent over PSA + C18 is clearly visible from 6 to 13 min. Compounds responsible for the difference between those two chromatograms were identified as saturated and unsaturated fatty acid and monoglycerides.

The difference between the typical QuEChERS clean-up (MgSO_4 , PSA, C18) and the clean-up applied in this work (MgSO_4 and Z-Sep) is the substitution of PSA for silica coated with zirconium dioxide. Therefore, the ZrO_2 properties are responsible for the cleaner extracts. As was mentioned in the introduction, zirconium dioxide is a good adsorbent of phospholipids, carboxylic acids (among them fatty acids) and proteins.

3.3. Real samples

The fully validated method was employed in real sample analysis. 25 avocado samples and 18 almond samples were bought in local shops in Almeria. None of the 25 avocado samples contained any of validated pesticides. Three almond samples were positive. Two of them contained methoxyfenozide in concentration 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ and 31 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$; in one sample kresoxim methyl (13 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) was detected. The European Union Maximum Residue Level values for these pesticides are: methoxyfenozide 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ and kresoxim methyl 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ [36]. Taking 50% uncertainty into account [37], the concentration of no pesticide exceeded the EU MRLs. Apart from the pesticides listed above, there were 26 further positive findings in 10 samples but these concentrations were below limits

of quantitation.

3.4. Quality control

During all the experiments quality of results was controlled in two stages. Extraction was controlled with two surrogate standards – triphenyl phosphate (TPP) and malathion- d_{10} . Extraction was considered as carried out correctly when recoveries of surrogate standards were in the range from 70 to 120% and RSD was lower than 20%. When those criteria had been not fulfilled extractions were repeated. Second stage was control of the injection. For this purpose dimethoate- d_6 was used. Set of injections was accepted if RSD of dimethoate- d_6 peak area was below 20%. When RSD had been higher injections were repeated. The quality control data are shown in Fig. 5.

Except TTP and deuterated standards also formetanate, hexythiazox and oxamyl should be controlled. Those three pesticides were successfully validated however inter-day variability at level 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ in avocado was equal 20%.

4. Conclusions

High oil samples present special difficulties during the analysis. Well known sample preparation protocols such as QuEChERS, the ethyl acetate method and miniLuke had difficulties with extraction of pesticides from avocado and almonds. A good solution to overcome problems is the application of sorbent containing ZrO_2 . Out of two tested sorbents, Z-Sep and Z-Sep+, the first assured good recoveries for a higher number of pesticides. Z-Sep sorbent removed more matrix components than PSA + C18. It is advantage not only from point of view of analysis, but also from point of view of system maintenance. Apart from the application of a suitable sorbent, the method for sample reconstitution after evaporation (if it is applied) is also very important. Reconstitution in a mixture of 1:9 (v/v) acetonitrile: water was inefficient. In avocado, in order to achieve good recoveries for a large number of pesticides, it was necessary to increase the amount of acetonitrile to 30%. Almond samples, on the other hand, required 40% acetonitrile. Almonds are the more difficult matrix: out of 113 pesticides, 94 were at the 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ level and 92 were at the 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ level with recoveries ranging from 70 to 120%; whereas for avocado, there were 107 at both levels.

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Fig. 1. (a) percentage of total number of evaluated pesticides with recoveries from the range 70 to 120%, in avocado. Red bars: evaporation of 0.50 mL, reconstitution in 0.05 mL of ACN + 0.45 mL of H₂O; blue bars: evaporation of 0.50 mL, reconstitution in 0.30 mL of ACN + 0.70 mL of H₂O; (b) percentage of total number of evaluated pesticides with recoveries from the range 70 to 120% in almonds using Z-Sep sorbent. Comparison of different reconstitution methods. Evaporated volume 0.5 mL. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of the article.)

Fig. 2. Effect of pK_{ow} on pesticides recoveries from almond.

Fig. 3. LC-QToF full scan chromatograms of avocado extracts cleaned with two different sorbents.

Fig. 4. LC-QToF full scan chromatograms almond extracts cleaned with two different sorbents.

Fig. 5. (a) RSD of quality control compounds; (b) recoveries of quality control compounds. Injections made from 26th October until 24th January.

Table 1. Acquisition and chromatographic parameters for the selected compounds analysed by LC-MS/MS.

Compound	t_R (min)	SRM1	CE1 (V)	SRM2	CE2 (V)
Acephate	3.11	184/143	5	184/125	15
Acetamiprid	10.99	223/126	20	223/56	15
Aldicarb	13.58	213/89	15	213/116	10
Azinphos-methyl	20.17	318/132	8	318/261	0
Azoxystrobin	20.80	404/372	10	404/344	20
Bitertanol	21.81	338/269	5	338/99	10
Boscalid	21.06	343/307	16	343/272	32
Bromuconazole	20.26; 21.28	378/159	20	378/70	20
Bupirimate	19.25	317/166	20	317/272	20
Buprofezin	24.59	306/201	10	306/116	15
Carbaryl	16.90	202/145	10	202/127	20
Carbendazim	3.31	192/160	15	192/132	20
Chlorantraniliprole	18.76	484/286	8	484/453	16
Chlorpyrifos	28.07	350/198	20	350/97	20
Chlorpyrifos-methyl	27.47	322/125	16	322/290	14
Clofentezine	24.66	303/138	12	303/102	40
Cymoxanil	12.47	199/128	4	199/111	12
Cyproconazole	19.85	292/70	16	292/125	32
Cyprodinil	18.71	226/93	40	226/77	40
Cyromazine	2.28	167/85	20	167/125	15
Diazinon	25.03	305/169	15	305/153	20
Dicrotophos	5.53	238/112	8	238/72	28
Diethofencarb	20.31	268/226	5	268/180	15
Difenoconazole	23.45	406/251	20	406/337	15
Dimethoate	10.89	230/199	5	230/171	10
Dimethoate- d_6	10.88	236/205	4	236/131	16
Dimethomorph	18.56; 18.99	388/301	20	388/165	20
Diniconazole	22.74	326/70	28	326/159	28
Diphenylamine	22.95	170/93	32	170/65	36
Dodine	17.91	228/57	20	228/60	20
Ethion	28.33	385/199	5	385/171	10
Ethirimol	6.62	210/140	20	210/43	52
Ethoprophos	21.57	243/131	15	243/97	30
Fenamidone	21.18	312/92	28	312/65	56
Fenamiphos	20.59	304/217	20	304/234	12
Fenarimol	20.25	331/268	20	331/259	20
Fenazaquin	27.47	307/161	15	307/147	15
Fenbuconazole	21.81	337/70	33	337/125	40
Fenoxycarb	22.37	302/88	20	302/116	5
Fenpropathrin	28.07	350/97	32	350/125	10
Fenpropimorph	15.84	304/147	30	304/130	25
Fenpyroximate	27.91	422/366	12	422/107	64
Fenthion	24.36	279/247	8	279/169	12
Fluazifop	20.09	328/282	15	328/254	20
Flufenoxuron	27.28	489/158	20	489/141	56
Fluquinconazole	21.22	376/307	24	376/108	56
Flusilazole	21.76	316/247	12	316/165	24
Flutriafol	16.72	302/70	16	302/95	56
Formetanate	2.97	222/65	52	222/165	8
Haloxyfop	22.18	362/316	12	362/288	24
Hexythiazox	28.04	353/228	10	353/168	20
Imazalil	13.69	297/159	20	297/255	15
Imidacloprid	9.98	256/209	15	256/175	15
Indoxacarb	25.94	528/203	45	528/150	20
Iprovalicarb	20.79	321/119	16	321/203	0
Isofenphos-methyl	25.14	231/121	15	231/199	15
Isoprocarb	18.45	194/95	15	194/152	5
Kresoxim-methyl	23.91	314/267	0	314/222	10
Linuron	20.35	249/160	20	249/133	36
Malathion	22.74	331/127	10	331/99	20
Malathion- d_{10}	22.76	341/132	12	341/100	24
Mandipropamid	21.13	412/328	8	412/356	4
Metalaxyl	17.25	280/220	5	280/192	10
Metconazole	22.13	320/70	24	320/125	48
Methamidophos	3.07	142/94	10	142/125	10
Methidathion	20.39	303/145	0	303/85	15
Methiocarb	19.99	226/169	5	226/121	12
Methoxyfenozide	22.11	369/149	15	369/133	20
Metobromuron	18.26	259/170	15	259/148	10
Monocrotophos	4.66	224/193	5	224/127	10
Myclobutanil	20.93	289/70	15	289/125	20
Nitenpyram	4.38	271/225	10	271/99	10
Oxamyl	4.87	237/72	10	237/90	5

Oxydemeton-methyl	3.97	247/109	24	247/169	8
Paclobutrazole	19.42	294/70	16	294/125	36
Pencycuron	25.15	329/125	24	329/89	60
Pendimethalin	27.98	282/212	4	282/194	16
Phenthoate	24.73	321/247	4	321/79	44
Phosalone	25.47	368/182	8	368/111	44
Phosmet	20.74	318/160	8	318/133	26
Phoxim	25.59	299/129	4	299/77	24
Pirimicarb	6.61	239/72	20	239/182	15
Pirimiphos-methyl	25.04	306/164	20	306/108	20
Prochloraz	19.29	376/308	10	376/266	15
Profenofos	25.95	375/305	15	375/347	5
Propamocarb	3.07	189/102	15	189/144	10
Propiconazole	22.81	342/159	32	342/69	16
Propoxur	16.06	210/168	0	210/153	0
Propyzamide	21.65	256/190	10	256/173	20
Pymetrozine	2.36	218/105	20	218/51	60
Pyraclostrobin	24.47	388/194	8	388/163	20
Pyrethrins	29.14	329/161	5	329/143	20
Pyridaben	29.34	365/309	10	365/147	20
Pyrimethanil	15.33	200/107	20	200/183	20
Pyriproxyfen	27.13	322/96	10	322/185	20
Quinoxyfen	25.64	308/197	35	308/272	25
Rotenone	22.30	395/213	20	395/192	20
Spinosyn A	17.36	732/142	20	732/98	20
Spinosyn D	18.16	746/142	20	746/98	20
Spirodiclofen	30.19	411/71	15	411/313	5
Spiromesifen	30.08	371/273	5	371/255	20
Tebuconazole	21.41	308/70	20	308/125	20
Tebufenozide	23.49	353/133	15	353/297	5
Tebufenpyrad	26.03	344/145	20	344/171	20
Tetraconazole	21.58	372/159	36	372/70	20
Trichlorfon	8.30	257/221	4	257/109	12
Thiabendazole	3.50	202/175	30	202/131	40
Thiacloprid	12.97	253/126	20	253/186	10
Thiamethoxam	7.12	292/211	10	292/181	20
Thiophanate-methyl	15.30	343/151	20	343/93	56
TPP	24.35	327/77	35	327/152	30
Triadimefon	21.35	294/197	10	294/225	10
Triazophos	22.57	314/162	20	314/286	10
Triflumuron	23.82	359/156	8	359/139	32
Triticonazole	19.55	318/70	33	318/125	41
Zoxamide	24.65	336/187	16	336/159	44

Table 2. Recoveries and relative standard deviation at 10 and 50 µg/kg (n = 5) in the two matrices.

Compound	Avocado				Almonds			
	10 µg/kg		50 µg/kg		10 µg/kg		50 µg/kg	
	Rec, %	RSD, %						
Acephate	79	7	76	7	73	7	78	4
Acetamiprid	107	2	101	1	93	1	99	1
Aldicarb	103	3	94	2	88	1	95	4
Azinphos-methyl	114	3	99	4	83	2	92	3
Azoxystrobin	95	3	92	4	79	5	102	2
Bitertanol	92	3	89	2	82	2	97	1
Boscalid	104	5	89	4	83	3	91	1
Bromuconazole	98	5	87	2	76	4	94	1
Bupirimate	97	1	86	4	74	3	87	2
Buprofezin	91	1	94	3	48	3	61	3
Carbaryl	102	2	90	2	74	3	94	1
Carbendazim	93	4	91	6	83	1	87	4
Chlorantraniliprole	98	1	92	3	95	2	102	2
Chlorpyrifos	107	5	72	4	58	8	55	7
Chlorpyrifos-methyl	97	3	75	3	74	8	72	4
Clofentezine	88	15	86	5	71	4	73	3
Cymoxanil	104	3	100	1	88	1	104	2
Cyproconazole	98	3	91	2	79	3	92	3
Cyprodinil	80	5	75	2	47	3	60	1
Cyromazine	48	1	44	10	69	1	71	14
Diazinon	93	4	87	3	83	1	81	2
Dicrotophos	97	1	88	2	78	3	94	2
Diethofencarb	106	4	92	2	81	1	98	3
Difenoconazole	90	4	86	1	70	1	88	1
Dimethoate	107	2	99	1	70	2	99	1
Dimethomorph	94	2	92	1	83	5	103	3
Diniconazole	95	2	81	3	70	2	86	1
Diphenylamine	87	2	74	3	70	1	70	2
Dodine	112	4	106	8	72	3	85	4
Ethion	119	5	84	2	56	5	67	6
Ethirimol	54	6	55	3	75	1	71	4
Ethoprophos	95	3	84	2	77	3	87	2
Fenamidone	105	4	92	1	82	2	98	2
Fenamiphos	95	2	80	3	83	2	98	2
Fenarimol	95	3	84	2	72	7	86	3
Fenazaquin	70	4	72	1	26	2	42	4
Fenbuconazole	98	5	92	3	87	2	104	1
Fenoxycarb	105	5	102	2	80	1	93	4
Fenpropathrin	100	4	76	3	53	8	60	4
Fenpropimorph	94	5	86	2	59	5	57	8
Fenpyroximate	87	4	77	3	50	1	67	4
Fenthion	109	2	106	8	75	2	80	3
Fluazifop	89	3	83	2	36	2	38	5
Flufenoxuron	103	5	98	12	61	7	71	4
Fluquinconazole	115	1	91	4	74	7	91	1
Flusilazole	98	3	92	2	77	5	100	1
Flutriafol	102	1	94	2	82	1	99	2
Formetanate	92	2	86	3	82	2	80	2
Haloxifop	85	4	85	5	37	4	40	3
Hexythiazox	95	3	89	6	41	5	49	5
Imazalil	78	2	78	2	88	3	84	3
Imidacloprid	98	1	101	1	80	1	100	2
Indoxacarb	99	6	92	2	77	2	95	2
Iprovalicarb	73	4	91	2	82	2	104	1
Isofenphos-methyl	105	1	98	4	76	2	88	2
Isoprocarb	92	2	91	1	87	1	98	1
Kresoxim-methyl	99	1	91	3	79	2	97	3
Linuron	94	3	90	2	82	7	91	2
Malathion	96	3	93	2	88	2	99	3
Mandipropamid	107	3	94	2	96	8	110	2
Metalaxyl	98	2	95	1	92	2	104	2
Metconazole	95	4	88	2	79	2	92	1
Methamidophos	78	3	72	6	46	1	63	1
Methidathion	78	3	95	1	86	3	94	2
Methiocarb	106	2	92	2	85	3	90	2
Methoxyfenozide	99	2	99	2	97	4	104	4
Metobromuron	94	3	92	2	89	1	94	2
Monocrotophos	91	1	91	2	83	1	96	1
Myclobutanil	101	4	93	1	91	2	100	2

Nitenpyram	34	1	33	8	61	6	57	9
Oxamyl	81	13	94	5	84	8	100	2
Oxydemeton-methyl	91	2	89	2	87	2	88	1
Paclobutrazole	96	3	94	1	90	1	98	1
Pencycuron	96	1	95	3	75	2	80	4
Pendimethalin	105	4	73	7	47	2	53	6
Phenthoate	92	2	94	6	80	4	90	2
Phosalone	106	11	105	7	83	1	81	2
Phosmet	103	4	93	2	84	1	89	3
Phoxim	99	4	101	3	82	9	87	4
Pirimicarb	84	4	88	3	86	2	94	1
Pirimiphos-methyl	95	3	83	2	77	2	76	2
Prochloraz	85	2	80	3	77	1	91	4
Profenofos	90	1	85	4	76	3	75	1
Propamocarb	79	3	78	2	71	1	76	1
Propiconazole	95	3	87	3	82	1	89	2
Propoxur	93	2	96	3	90	2	101	1
Propyzamide	93	2	93	3	84	1	91	3
Pymetrozine	39	6	46	7	37	1	67	4
Pyraclostrobin	103	1	82	2	78	1	88	4
Pyrethrins	99	7	96	4	48	14	61	8
Pyridaben	81	4	79	10	38	3	48	7
Pyrimethanil	90	3	85	2	71	2	73	1
Pyriproxyfen	91	1	88	4	55	4	58	6
Quinoxifen	68	4	46	1	41	2	45	3
Rotenone	93	3	92	4	81	3	96	3
Spinosyn A	96	3	98	1	78	1	95	2
Spinosyn D	94	3	100	1	75	5	92	2
Spirodiclofen	104	6	115	1	71	1	74	2
Spiromesifen	116	6	97	5	72	6	76	3
Tebuconazole	96	3	93	1	82	3	93	2
Tebufenozide	98	4	102	1	89	1	101	2
Tebufenpyrad	87	3	82	2	75	4	70	2
Tetraconazole	93	3	95	4	97	1	111	2
Thiabendazole	79	2	77	2	94	9	85	7
Thiacloprid	108	2	107	1	85	2	101	2
Thiamethoxam	113	2	109	1	79	2	98	1
Thiophanate-methyl	11	28	21	3	107	5	94	4
Triadimefon	99	3	94	2	92	4	96	2
Triazophos	95	3	94	1	89	2	98	2
Trichlorfon	99	2	100	2	91	1	95	2
Triflumuron	101	6	86	4	77	8	91	2
Triticonazole	96	2	91	1	86	2	98	1
Zoxamide	95	4	96	3	81	3	89	1

Table 3. Limits of quantification, concentration range and matrix effects for the selected matrices studied.

Compound	LOQ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)		R^2		Instrumental concentration range ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)		ME (%) = $\left(\frac{\text{slope matrix}}{\text{slope solvent}} - 1\right) \times 100$	
	Avocado	Almonds	Avocado	Almonds	Avocado	Almonds	Avocado	Almonds
Acephate	10	10	0.9971	0.9973	10–500	10–500	-26	-29
Acetamiprid	10	10	0.9979	0.9943	1–500	1–500	-17	-13
Aldicarb	10	10	0.9966	0.9909	1–500	1–500	-60	-48
Azinphos-methyl	10	10	0.9988	0.9995	2–500	1–500	-20	-3
Azoxystrobin	10	10	0.9997	0.9973	1–500	1–500	-2	-6
Bitertanol	10	10	0.9980	0.9984	1–500	1–500	-12	-3
Boscalid	10	10	0.9970	0.9971	1–500	1–500	-40	-4
Bromuconazole	10	10	0.9979	0.9997	2–500	1–500	-4	2
Bupirimate	10	10	0.9909	0.9929	1–500	1–500	-1	-1
Buprofezin	10	-	0.9970	0.9966	1–500	1–500	-59	-2
Carbaryl	10	10	0.9927	0.9993	2–500	2–500	-19	-14
Carbendazim	10	10	0.9923	0.9970	1–500	1–500	-43	-48
Chlorantraniliprole	10	10	0.9983	0.9994	1–500	1–500	-7	-2
Chlorpyrifos	10	-	0.9996	0.9997	2–500	1–500	-80	-3
Chlorpyrifos-methyl	10	10	0.9993	0.9994	2–500	1–500	-48	-7
Clofentezine	10	10	0.9990	0.9997	2–500	1–500	-43	-1
Cymoxanil	10	10	0.9997	0.9997	2–500	1–500	-4	-4
Cyproconazole	10	10	0.9982	0.9951	1–500	1–500	-15	-8
Cyprodinil	10	-	0.9944	0.9956	1–500	1–500	-20	-6
Cyromazine	-	50	0.9950	0.9914	2–500	1–500	-74	-49
Diazinon	10	10	0.9967	0.9978	1–500	1–500	-30	0
Dicrotophos	10	10	0.9937	0.9987	1–500	1–500	-11	-14
Diethofencarb	10	10	0.9964	0.9999	1–500	1–500	-16	-1
Difenoconazole	10	10	0.9946	0.9995	1–500	1–500	-23	1
Dimethoate	10	10	0.9960	0.9964	1–500	1–500	-11	-19
Dimethomorph	10	10	0.9975	0.9995	1–500	1–500	-5	-9
Diniconazole	10	10	0.9909	0.9979	1–500	1–500	-9	-2
Diphenylamine	10	10	0.9921	0.9967	1–500	1–500	-13	-1
Dodine	10	10	0.9968	0.9994	10–500	1–500	-34	-14
Ethion	10	-	0.9986	0.9954	1–500	1–500	-76	-8
Ethirimol	-	10	0.9964	0.9981	1–500	1–500	-15	-16
Ethoprophos	10	10	0.9904	0.9943	2–500	1–500	-30	-6
Fenamidone	10	10	0.9918	0.9938	2–500	1–500	-37	0
Fenamiphos	10	10	0.9908	0.9965	2–500	1–500	-7	2
Fenarimol	10	10	0.9992	1.0000	1–500	1–500	-8	-1
Fenazaquin	10	-	0.9947	0.9938	1–500	1–500	-57	1
Fenbuconazole	10	10	0.9983	0.9964	1–500	1–500	-10	1
Fenoxycarb	10	10	0.9980	0.9985	1–500	1–500	-30	2
Fenpropathrin	10	-	0.9991	0.9997	1–500	1–500	-79	2
Fenpropimorph	10	-	0.9964	0.9910	1–500	1–500	-20	-5
Fenpyroximate	10	-	0.9992	0.9904	1–200	1–500	-28	-32
Fenthion	10	10	0.9967	0.9999	1–500	1–500	-52	-5
Fluazifop	10	-	0.9991	0.9976	1–500	1–500	-19	1
Flufenoxuron	10	50	0.9949	0.9985	1–500	1–500	-72	1
Fluquinconazole	10	10	0.9984	0.9993	1–500	1–500	-23	-1
Flusilazole	10	10	0.9975	0.9916	1–500	1–500	-9	-1
Flutriafol	10	10	0.9978	0.9959	1–500	1–500	-3	0
Formetanate	10	10	0.9984	0.9907	1–200	1–500	-9	-34
Haloxyfop	10	-	0.9953	0.9966	1–500	1–500	-15	-4
Hexythiazox	10	-	0.9957	0.9956	2–500	1–500	-66	-10
Imazalil	10	10	0.9998	0.9994	2–500	2–500	-23	-11
Imidacloprid	10	10	0.9997	0.9995	1–500	1–500	-13	-9
Indoxacarb	10	10	0.9990	0.9990	1–500	1–500	-44	-2
Iprovalicarb	10	10	0.9956	0.9995	2–500	1–500	1	17
Isofenphos-methyl	10	10	0.9994	0.9960	1–500	1–500	3	2
Isoprocarb	10	10	0.9971	0.9989	1–500	1–500	-7	-6
Kresoxim-methyl	10	10	0.9994	0.9993	1–500	1–500	-27	-5
Linuron	10	10	0.9991	0.9998	1–500	1–500	-18	-2
Malathion	10	10	0.9969	0.9992	1–500	1–500	-13	-6
Mandipropamid	10	10	0.9937	0.9976	1–500	1–500	-34	3
Metalaxyl	10	10	0.9998	0.9969	1–200	1–500	4	-1
Metconazole	10	10	0.9938	0.9999	1–500	1–500	-19	27
Methamidophos	10	-	0.9986	1.0000	2–500	1–500	-17	-10
Methidathion	10	10	0.9985	0.9995	1–500	1–500	-22	0
Methiocarb	10	10	0.9999	0.9991	1–500	1–500	-32	-4
Methoxyfenozide	10	10	0.9959	0.9950	2–500	1–500	-7	-1
Metobromuron	10	10	0.9995	0.9997	2–500	1–500	-6	-4
Monocrotophos	10	10	0.9901	0.9960	2–500	1–500	-6	-15
Myclobutanil	10	10	0.9907	0.9966	2–500	1–500	-10	-4
Nitenpyram	-	-	0.9928	0.9959	2–500	1–500	-30	2

Oxamyl	10	10	0.9945	0.9998	10-500	10-500	-17	-49
Oxydemeton-methyl	10	10	0.9974	0.9990	1-500	1-500	-6	-6
Paclobutrazole	10	10	0.9972	0.9958	1-500	1-500	-6	-1
Pencycuron	10	10	0.9915	0.9973	1-200	1-500	-49	-4
Pendimethalin	10	-	0.9981	0.9975	2-500	1-500	-65	-7
Phenthoate	10	10	0.9981	0.9985	10-500	1-500	-26	-8
Phosalone	10	10	0.9927	0.9992	2-500	1-500	-58	-5
Phosmet	10	10	0.9999	0.9978	1-500	1-500	-46	-7
Phoxim	10	10	0.9996	0.9999	2-500	2-500	-41	-2
Pirimicarb	10	10	0.9902	0.9976	1-500	1-500	-4	-8
Pirimiphos-methyl	10	10	0.9998	0.9952	1-500	1-500	-39	-2
Prochloraz	10	10	0.9902	0.9986	1-500	1-500	-13	-6
Profenofos	10	10	0.9964	0.9996	1-500	1-500	-34	-2
Propamocarb	10	10	0.9985	0.9922	1-200	1-500	-11	-18
Propiconazole	10	10	0.9988	1.0000	1-500	2-500	-14	0
Propoxur	10	10	0.9947	0.9976	1-500	1-500	-16	-13
Propyzamide	10	10	0.9984	0.9987	1-200	1-500	-15	-2
Pymetrozine	-	-	0.9993	0.9986	1-50	1-200	-49	-57
Pyraclostrobin	10	10	0.9969	0.9921	1-200	1-500	-22	-3
Pyrethrins	10	-	0.9976	0.9998	10-500	2-500	-71	-16
Pyridaben	10	-	0.9910	0.9990	1-200	1-500	-79	-5
Pyrimethanil	10	10	0.9941	0.9983	1-500	1-500	-35	-7
Pyriproxyfen	10	-	0.9966	0.9996	1-500	1-500	-66	1
Quinoxifen	-	-	0.9944	0.9922	1-500	1-500	-30	-1
Rotenone	10	10	0.9981	0.9986	1-500	1-500	-24	-7
Spinosyn A	10	10	0.9974	0.9903	1-200	1-500	-19	-35
Spinosyn D	10	10	0.9993	0.9981	1-500	1-500	-28	-20
Spirodiclofen	10	10	0.9980	0.9909	10-500	1-500	-84	-12
Spiromesifen	10	10	0.9995	0.9940	2-500	1-500	-84	-28
Tebuconazole	10	10	0.9968	0.9928	1-500	1-500	-15	-23
Tebufenozide	10	10	0.9954	0.9944	1-500	1-500	-8	-1
Tebufenpyrad	10	10	0.9966	0.9951	1-500	1-500	-37	-3
Tetraconazole	10	10	0.9968	0.9934	1-500	1-500	-11	-2
Thiabendazole	10	10	0.9990	0.9925	1-500	1-500	-26	-28
Thiacloprid	10	10	0.9981	0.9936	1-500	1-500	-43	-12
Thiamethoxam	10	10	0.9983	0.9902	1-500	1-500	-17	-13
Thiophanatemethyl	-	10	0.9939	0.9941	2-500	1-500	-40	-6
Triadimefon	10	10	0.9925	0.9975	1-500	1-500	-9	-2
Triazophos	10	10	0.9999	0.9988	1-500	1-500	-9	1
Trichlorfon	10	10	0.9999	0.9997	1-500	1-500	3	19
Triflumuron	10	10	0.9997	0.9976	2-500	1-500	-68	-4
Triticonazole	10	10	0.9986	0.9952	1-500	1-500	-7	-2
Zoxamide	10	10	0.9951	0.9987	2-500	1-500	-23	-3

Table S1. Comparison of recoveries of pesticides from avocado at 50 µg/kg with different clean-up methods and different reconstitution solvents according to their pK_{ow}.

Pesticide	PSA/C18		Z-Sep		pK _{ow}
	GC (EtAc)	LC (30% ACN)	GC (EtAc)	LC (30% ACN)	
Pyridaben	85%	37%	80%	79%	6.37
Fenpropathrin	113%	45%	91%	76%	6.00
Spirodiclofen	84%	32%	92%	115%	5.83
Fenazaquin	77%	35%	67%	72%	5.51
Pyriproxyfen	83%	36%	81%	88%	5.37
Pendimethalin	90%	36%	76%	73%	5.20
Ethion	91%	37%	90%	84%	5.07
Tebufenpyrad	83%	45%	87%	82%	4.93
Chlorpyrifos	83%	36%	81%	72%	4.70
Quinoxifen	72%	37%	67%	46%	4.66
Indoxacarb	90%	46%	99%	92%	4.65
Fenpropimorph	84%	67%	92%	86%	4.50
Profenofos	85%	48%	84%	85%	4.44
Pirimiphos Methyl	88%	76%	89%	83%	4.20
Chlorpyrifos Methyl	80%	52%	81%	75%	4.00
Cyprodinil	78%	66%	85%	75%	4.00
Pyraclostrobin	98%	55%	89%	82%	3.99
Flusilazole	91%	75%	92%	92%	3.87
Metconazole	88%	72%	92%	88%	3.85
Parathion Ethyl	99%	67%	91%	97%	3.83
Diphenylamine	76%	66%	78%	74%	3.82
Fenbuconazole	97%	75%	97%	92%	3.79
Propiconazole	91%	72%	90%	87%	3.72
Tebuconazole	93%	77%	92%	93%	3.70
Fenarimol	163%	77%	91%	84%	3.69
Phenthoate	100%	69%	94%	94%	3.69
Bupirimate	77%	81%	95%	86%	3.68
Isofenphos Methyl	91%	72%	93%	98%	3.59
Tetraconazol	89%	80%	93%	95%	3.56
Kresoxim methyl	95%	77%	99%	91%	3.40
Triazophos	97%	81%	96%	94%	3.34
Fluquinconazole	89%	83%	93%	91%	3.24
Myclobutanil	91%	87%	96%	93%	3.17

Paclobutrazole	82%	89%	94%	94%	3.11
Triadimefon	96%	85%	99%	94%	3.11
Ethoprophos	85%	82%	89%	84%	3.10
Cyproconazole	92%	88%	93%	91%	3.09
Propyzamide	91%	82%	90%	93%	3.00
Pyrimethanil	89%	81%	86%	85%	3.00
Boscalid	88%	83%	95%	89%	2.96
Phosmet	107%	92%	94%	93%	2.96
Fenamidone	96%	88%	94%	92%	2.80
Malathion	98%	88%	99%	93%	2.75
Azoxystrobin	93%	95%	97%	92%	2.50
Methidathion	94%	87%	93%	95%	2.20
Metalaxyl	87%	96%	95%	95%	1.75
Pirimicarb	88%	87%	89%	88%	1.70
Acephate	87%	115%	82%	76%	-0.85

Table S2. Precision of the chromatographic method in the different matrices (n=5) at 10 and 50 µg/kg.

Compound	Intra-day variability (RSD, %)				Inter-day variability (RSD, %)			
	10 µg/kg		50 µg/kg		10 µg/kg		50 µg/kg	
	Avocado	Almonds	Avocado	Almonds	Avocado	Almonds	Avocado	Almonds
Acephate	3	3	1	5	11	5	7	6
Acetamiprid	1	1	1	1	6	8	4	9
Aldicarb	5	6	2	3	17	13	9	10
Azinphos-methyl	2	2	2	2	10	6	4	8
Azoxystrobin	1	3	2	2	9	8	6	11
Bitertanol	3	1	2	1	9	8	7	10
Boscalid	1	1	1	2	13	12	9	14
Bromuconazole	1	2	3	2	10	9	6	11
Bupirimate	3	2	2	2	12	15	8	16
Buprofezin	2	2	2	2	7	3	5	6
Carbaryl	4	4	1	1	6	11	6	6
Carbendazim	1	1	1	1	9	6	5	6
Chlorantraniliprole	1	2	1	3	12	6	8	8
Chlorpyrifos	1	1	4	3	15	11	17	10
Chlorpyrifos-methyl	6	5	3	9	8	15	3	18
Clofentezine	4	1	2	6	11	9	8	12
Cymoxanil	2	2	2	3	10	10	7	10
Cyproconazole	1	3	2	1	10	7	6	8
Cyprodinil	3	1	3	4	12	8	7	11
Cyromazine	2	5	2	5	8	10	4	7
Diazinon	3	3	1	4	15	3	10	3
Diclotophos	2	2	1	7	13	5	10	10
Diethofencarb	2	1	2	2	8	9	9	11
Difenoconazole	5	1	1	5	17	8	10	12
Dimethoate	1	1	1	2	6	4	5	6
Dimethomorph	2	1	1	3	6	12	3	14
Diniconazole	1	1	2	4	7	9	4	12
Diphenylamine	1	1	1	1	6	3	2	1
Dodine	5	6	7	2	19	7	16	13
Ethion	5	4	4	1	18	10	16	12
Ethirimol	1	1	1	1	9	4	5	10
Ethoprofos	2	3	1	1	9	10	6	11
Fenamidone	1	3	1	1	10	6	9	7
Fenamiphos	2	1	1	3	10	10	5	9
Fenarimol	1	4	1	2	13	10	6	11
Fenazaquin	6	1	5	4	7	10	7	14
Fenbuconazole	3	1	3	3	11	9	8	12
Fenoxycarb	2	3	2	1	15	10	13	11
Fenpropathrin	8	1	8	3	16	10	11	7
Fenpropimorph	1	1	1	4	12	5	8	8
Fenpyroximate	2	1	8	7	6	12	7	16
Fenthion	1	4	3	4	12	16	9	16
Fluazifop	1	4	1	1	10	6	5	8

Flufenoxuron	5	1	8	2	18	15	13	2
Fluquinconazole	3	1	4	4	12	14	11	15
Flusilazole	1	1	1	2	10	7	5	10
Flutriafol	2	1	1	2	11	6	6	8
Formetanate	1	2	2	2	20	9	14	9
Haloxyfop	2	1	1	2	9	12	3	12
Hexythiazox	5	3	7	1	20	6	15	6
Imazalil	4	1	1	4	10	4	7	8
Imidacloprid	1	1	1	1	11	10	8	9
Indoxacarb	6	2	1	2	9	13	5	17
Iprovalicarb	4	1	1	3	6	7	6	8
Isofenphos-Methyl	3	2	1	4	11	4	12	9
Isoprocab	1	1	1	3	3	7	4	9
Kresoxim-methyl	1	1	1	1	6	4	2	6
Linuron	2	1	2	1	9	9	5	10
Malathion	2	3	1	2	4	11	2	10
Mandipropamid	3	2	1	2	8	8	5	9
Metalaxyl	1	1	1	3	7	9	3	9
Metconazole	1	1	2	2	4	8	4	10
Methamidophos	2	1	1	3	11	7	8	12
Methidathion	1	1	1	2	7	11	4	11
Methiocarb	1	1	2	1	7	8	7	11
Methoxyfenozide	1	1	1	2	4	3	6	6
Metobromuron	1	2	1	2	10	9	6	10
Monocrotophos	1	1	1	4	8	7	4	10
Myclobutanil	1	1	2	1	6	8	3	9
Nitenpyram	2	1	1	2	10	5	4	8
Oxamyl	2	12	2	5	20	14	14	15
Oxydemeton-methyl	1	1	1	4	10	9	4	11
Paclobutrazole	1	1	1	2	6	7	2	8
Pencycuron	6	4	4	3	5	6	3	10
Pendimethalin	3	2	4	1	8	4	6	4
Phenthoate	5	2	4	5	14	14	4	17
Phosalone	1	2	1	1	11	13	6	14
Phosmet	4	6	2	5	18	13	8	14
Phoxim	6	2	4	10	13	13	10	16
Pirimicarb	2	2	1	1	8	6	3	6
Pirimiphos-methyl	1	2	1	2	3	7	2	7
Prochloraz	2	1	2	3	6	8	2	11
Profenofos	1	1	2	2	10	10	5	13
Propamocarb	2	3	2	6	6	6	3	10
Propiconazole	3	3	2	1	7	7	4	7
Propoxur	1	3	1	1	4	7	2	7
Propyzamide	3	2	1	1	9	9	5	11
Pymetrozine	1	2	1	3	18	8	10	10
Pyraclostrobin	2	3	2	3	7	9	6	9
Pyrethrins	6	3	5	2	15	13	8	14
Pyridaben	4	3	2	4	11	15	6	17
Pyrimethanil	2	1	1	2	6	7	2	10

Pyriproxyfen	6	3	6	2	11	5	6	7
Quinoxifen	8	2	7	1	11	8	8	9
Rotenone	1	1	1	1	12	11	9	11
Spinosyn A	1	1	2	2	3	10	4	8
Spinosyn D	1	2	1	4	4	8	4	9
Spirodiclofen	3	7	4	4	17	18	10	4
Spiromesifen	6	11	2	5	7	17	4	5
Tebuconazole	1	2	1	1	5	8	4	10
Tebufenozide	1	1	1	1	6	4	6	11
Tebufenpyrad	5	2	4	1	7	10	5	11
Tetraconazole	2	2	2	1	6	10	3	10
Thiabendazole	1	1	1	9	11	16	7	13
Thiacloprid	1	1	2	8	13	6	8	10
Thiamethoxam	1	5	1	1	7	8	4	10
Thiophanate-methyl	5	2	6	3	8	11	7	14
Triadimefon	1	1	2	2	6	9	3	9
Triazophos	1	1	2	1	5	6	4	9
Trichlorfon	1	2	1	2	3	17	5	20
Triflumuron	5	1	3	2	13	12	13	13
Triticonazole	1	1	1	1	8	6	4	7
Zoxamide	4	3	3	1	6	11	4	11

Fig. S1

Fat content in the final avocado extracts

Ethyl acetate
method

miniLuke

QuEChERS
with Z-Sep